

The Coupling Constant Series and Total Variations Pairing

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June 8, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the procedure in which the coupling constant series was obtained, and in particular, the total pairings of variations, it is possible to extrapolate an additional insight on the flexibility of the process. The commutation relation of the elements and the invariance to the element value themselves as long as the total sum of the pairing satisfies key conditions.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Primes set} \quad (2.1)$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P} \quad (2.2)$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (2.3)$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ...$$

We have obtain the net variation, N_V , as part of a total variation pair, (p_1, p_2) , which we required the sum to be two and three divisible. We gave two examples for the strong interaction:

$$(p_1, p_2) = (5, 13) \quad (3)$$

$$(p_1, p_2) = (7, 11) \quad (3.1)$$

Two points with regard to those pairs. First, it is commutative, we can replace the elements in the pair and nature will be invariant, the coupling series will hold:

$$(p_1, p_2) \rightarrow (p_2, p_1) \quad (3.11)$$

Nature is invariant to the actual value of the elements; we can choose any two primes, as long as their sum creating an even number, two and three divisible of certain magnitude, the coupling constant will hold as well. In the 8T thesis we chosen the first pair, it could have worked exactly as well with the second pair.

$$(p_1 + p_2) = S1 \quad (3.12)$$

$$(p_3 + p_4) = S1 \quad (3.13)$$

An additional point that was not mentioned in the thesis, the coupling series will hold with any additional amount of primes clustering. We chose the simplest one, two primes in a pair. It could have been four, six or any even number of primes pairing. Any even amount of primes added will yield an even number. Of course the adjustment needed to be made regarding to the division, so we can reach the average value.

$$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N P_i}{N} = S1_{Average} \quad (3.14)$$

If we had four primes pairing, divide by four, six primes divide by six, to reach the average. Of course the average must be two and three divisible, so it could get harder and less likely to find higher numbers of primes pairing which satisfying the condition. It will be impossible to reach the smallest sum in the series with a hundred primes pairing. So for the beginning of the series there could be a limitation.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)